

Development of Interactive Poetry Writing Teaching Materials with Smart Themed Differentiated Learning Design in Class X SMA Brawijaya Smart School

Andrean Fahreza Nur Wicaksana¹, Khristin Sri Utami Nardiyana², Dyah Werdiningsih³, Hasan Busri⁴

^{1,2,3,4} Universitas Islam Malang, East Java, Indonesia

ABSTRACT

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Indonesian language and literature learning currently has many learning resources, but interactive learning resources that suit the needs of teachers and students are still rarely found. Existing learning resources are usually presented in full in textbooks. The learning material is presented in accordance with the basic competencies listed in the curriculum so that it looks less attractive to students. The aim of this research is to develop interactive poetry writing teaching materials with a SMART-themed differentiation learning design for class X SMA Brawijaya Smart School students. It is hoped that the development of teaching materials will help learning to write poetry. Development research steps include needs analysis, product development, conducting small group trials according to the setting in which the product is used, and revising the results of product trials. This research uses a development procedure adapted from the Borg & Gall development model which produces 7 steps, namely (1) information collection, (2) planning, (3) product draft development, (4) product validation, (5) feasibility testing, (6) product revision, and (7) final product. In this research, the data collection techniques used were through interview guides, validation sheets, and student questionnaires. The data analysis carried out involved descriptive analysis techniques, both qualitative and quantitative. The results of the development process have several main menus that can help students, such as homepage, introduction, learning objectives, materials, learning videos, and evaluation. Based on the results of the assessment, validation by content and language experts is included in the very appropriate/valid criteria, namely 97.2% and 95.8%. Likewise, the validation of learning and media design experts is included in the very feasible/valid criteria, namely 95.8% and 93.7%. The assessment of the student questionnaire also includes very appropriate/valid criteria, namely student characteristics of 81.3% and level of understanding of material regarding procedural texts of 83.7%. The results from the teacher questionnaire were assessed with very appropriate/valid criteria, namely the effectiveness and efficiency of teaching materials was 93.75%, the systematics of teaching materials was 87.5%, the language was 100%, and the appearance of teaching materials was 88.8%. The conclusion of this research is that the development of interactive poetry writing teaching materials with a SMART-themed differentiation learning design in class X SMA Brawijaya Smart School is very suitable/valid for use in the learning process. Suggestions for future research are to conduct in-depth trials on the effectiveness of web-based teaching material products with differentiated learning designs and disseminate web-based teaching material products with differentiated learning designs in schools that have the same characteristics.

KEYWORDS:

Development of Teaching Materials, Interactive Poetry, Differentiated Learning Design, Smart Themes

Corresponding Author: Andrean Fahreza Nur Wicaksana

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1. INTRODUCTION

In an effort to advance education in Indonesia, one way is through research and development (R&D). R&D is often interpreted as a process for developing new products or improving existing ones (Mulyana, 2020). The aim of development research is to assess changes over a certain period of time. Teachers develop teaching materials to meet

Andrean Fahreza Nur Wicaksana et al, Development of Interactive Poetry Writing Teaching Materials with Smart Themed Differentiated Learning Design in Class X SMA Brawijaya Smart School

curriculum demands, student characteristics, and solving learning problems. In the independent learning curriculum, schools set graduate competency standards, but teaching methods and materials are determined by educators. Therefore, teachers must be able to develop their own teaching materials.

Language skills include four aspects: listening, speaking, reading and writing (Niswariyana & Muhdar, 2021). These four aspects are interrelated and are generally acquired in stages: from listening, speaking, reading, to writing. Writing is the most complex language skill and involves the use of language and content processing (Sukirman, 2020). Writing is important for communication, expressing ideas, and enriching the human experience. The independent learning curriculum for Indonesian language subjects in class X includes basic competencies for producing texts, including poetry. Students are expected to be able to express ideas and feelings through concise and beautiful language (Ulfah et al., 2023). Poetry is an expression of thoughts and feelings that are beautifully arranged for readers to enjoy (Musdolifah et al., 2023). This competency is important so that students can respond to events around them politely, creatively and beautifully in the era of rapid technology.

Based on a questionnaire at SMA Brawijaya Smart School, learning to write poetry has not been optimal. Students have difficulty producing poetry due to the lack of reference for standard and beautiful words in Indonesian, as well as embarrassment about expressing what is in their hearts through writing. Apart from that, many of the available teaching materials do not suit the needs of teachers and students (Wijayanti & Zulaeha, 2015; Sugihastuti, 2007). Teachers tend to focus on theory without practice, making learning less interesting and difficult to understand. Interactive teaching materials are needed that are interesting and use different learning designs. These teaching materials must encourage students to participate independently (Werdiningsih et al., 2022). Teachers must develop teaching materials that can activate individual interest and raise awareness that writing poetry is easy and close to everyday life.

To improve learning to write poetry in class This design will guide teachers in planning, implementing and evaluating learning, as well as connecting it with real life. The benefits for researchers are obtaining references for similar research in other schools and direct experience with SMART-themed differentiation learning designs.

SMA Brawijaya Smart School has a vision to produce SMART graduates. This vision gives teachers the freedom to develop teaching materials according to a varied curriculum and according to student needs. This has a positive impact on learning methods that are more interesting and appropriate to various student characteristics and learning styles. The SMART jargon allows it to be used as an

opportunity for differentiation in the current independent learning curriculum. This concept is expected to be able to improve student learning outcomes in the aspects of attitudes, knowledge and skills. Apart from that, improving the quality of students in terms of character values can also be linked to the expected goals.

This design is expected to provide a learning experience that activates students with various activities, invites deep thinking, and becomes a habituation process in everyday life. This learning will provide experience as a learner (Learner Experience) which is internalized in students, shapes their attitudes and behavior, and makes them lifelong learners.

A prototype of interactive web-based poetry writing text teaching materials using Google Sites will be developed for class X SMA Brawijaya Smart School students. Google Sites provides materials, instructions, images, videos and learning modules, making it easier for students to understand the material in light and not boring language. This media was developed according to the independent curriculum with a differentiated learning design, can be accessed via laptop or cellphone, and is considered innovative technology that improves student achievement (Syakiroh, 2021).

This research encourages learning progress based on institutional competency, develops knowledge of Indonesian language learning technology based on the Google Sites web, and can be a reference in assessment through the responses of students and educators. Apart from that, this research is useful for researchers, namely being able to gain direct experience and being able to compare theory with field practice. Meanwhile, teachers can provide teaching materials according to the curriculum, enrich references, and increase effective communication with students.

The benefit for students is that they are able to provide learning that is more interesting, independent and easy to understand. The benefit for the school is that it can support poetry teaching, improve students' attitudes, knowledge and skills. On the other hand, other researchers can benefit from being a reference in similar research and developing quality teaching materials.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Development of Teaching Materials

Teaching materials, or learning materials, include knowledge, skills and attitudes that students must learn to achieve competency standards. Types of learning material include facts, concepts, principles, procedures, skills, and attitudes or values. Teaching materials are important because they must be in accordance with the curriculum objectives, giving teachers the freedom to develop them as long as they do not deviate from the stated objectives.

Teaching materials have three main functions: as a guide for teachers, a guide for students, and an evaluation tool. Teachers use teaching materials to direct learning

Andreas Fahreza Nur Wicaksana et al, Development of Interactive Poetry Writing Teaching Materials with Smart Themed Differentiated Learning Design in Class X SMA Brawijaya Smart School

activities and convey competencies that students must master. Students use it to direct learning activities and measure the achievement of learning outcomes in accordance with the indicators and basic competencies that have been formulated in the syllabus.

Teaching materials can be grouped into four types: print (handouts, books, modules, worksheets, brochures, leaflets, photos/images), audio (cassettes, radio, audio CDs), audiovisual (video CDs, films), and interactive (interactive CDs). Teaching materials function as guidelines for teachers, guidelines for students, and evaluation tools. It helps direct learning activities, measures learner achievement, and ensures competencies are taught or learned.

Teaching materials must have six components: study guides, competencies that must be achieved, supporting information, exercises, work instructions, and evaluation. This helps make teaching materials systematic and effective in supporting the learning process. The design of teaching materials must be adapted to learning needs and activities based on the material presented in class.

B. Web Based Learning

Web-based learning, also known as e-learning, utilizes internet technology for the educational process. This helps overcome learning problems and improves students' learning outcomes and motivation. Web-based learning models using platforms such as Google Sites and web-based e-modules are effective in increasing knowledge aspects and avoiding student boredom. The downside is dependence on an internet connection.

C. Learning to Write Interactive Poetry

Poetry is a literary work that expresses the poet's thoughts and feelings in language that is bound by rhythm, dimension, rhyme, lyric structure, and stanzas. Writing poetry involves visualizing and concretizing abstract things so that they can be realized in writing. The right learning method is very important so that the process of writing poetry by students is maximized.

Writing poetry requires a deep understanding of physical elements (diction, imagery, figure of speech, typography, concrete words, rhyme) and inner elements (theme, feeling, tone, message). Observations show that students' poetry writing skills still need to be improved, with more focus on the writing aspect rather than just reading poetry. Interactive learning can stimulate students' creativity and sensitivity to the surrounding environment.

D. SMART Theme Differentiated Learning

The Merdeka Curriculum gives students the freedom to determine their educational path, with a differentiated learning approach that adapts the learning process to meet the individual needs of students. This involves grouping based on needs, use of varied teaching methods, and ongoing formative assessment.

The SMART theme at SMA Brawijaya Smart School involves the development of teaching materials that are adapted to the school's vision and mission to produce graduates who are Spiritual, Motivated, Active, Respectful and Technological. This SMART concept allows teachers to develop interesting and varied teaching materials in accordance with the Merdeka Belajar curriculum.

Differentiated learning with the SMART theme is expected to be able to provide learning experiences that are in-depth and relevant to students' daily lives, as well as internalizing the expected character values and competencies.

III. RESULTS

The results of the development of interactive poetry writing teaching materials with SMART-themed differentiation learning design in class) product feasibility which includes validation, initial product revision, trials, and final product results. Meanwhile, the development results have several main menus that can help students, such as homepage, introduction, learning objectives, materials, learning videos, and evaluation. This is in line with the stages of developing teaching materials using the Borg and Gall model.

Based on the results of a series of expert validations and student trials, it can be concluded that the development of interactive poetry writing teaching materials with a SMART themed differentiation learning design in class X SMA BSS Malang is very suitable for use in the learning process.

IV. DISCUSSION

A. Needs Analysis

The initial stage in research and development is needs analysis, which aims to gather information before research begins. In this research, a needs analysis was carried out at SMA Brawijaya Smart School Malang through observation and distribution of questionnaires to teachers and students. This questionnaire aims to determine the needs for learning poetry texts in class X.

1. Teacher Needs Analysis

The questionnaire for teachers includes 14 questions and 1 suggestion which focuses on aspects such as students' mastery of poetry writing material, availability and quality of teaching materials, use of multimedia, evaluation and aesthetics of teaching materials. The results of the questionnaire showed that teachers felt the need for teaching materials that could motivate students, contain evaluations, and be equipped with multimedia such as videos and images.

2. Analysis of Student Needs

The questionnaire for students includes 15 questions and 1 suggestion that focuses on their interests, needs and preferences in learning Indonesian, especially poetry

Andreas Fahreza Nur Wicaksana et al, Development of Interactive Poetry Writing Teaching Materials with Smart Themed Differentiated Learning Design in Class X SMA Brawijaya Smart School

texts. The results show that students want interactive learning and use multimedia, such as videos from YouTube and websites, to make learning more interesting and easy to understand.

B. Product Development

Planning teaching materials based on the results of needs analysis, with a focus on ease of understanding, motivation, curriculum achievements, learning objectives, examples, evaluations, attractive displays and learning videos.

The product draft developed is rhyme-based poetry text teaching materials with a SMART-themed differentiation learning design using Google Sites. Google Sites is used to upload material, provide assignments and evaluations which can be accessed by students via the internet.

1. . Main Menu Page: The initial display contains the title and learning topic, as well as menus such as home, objectives, materials, videos and evaluation.
2. Introduction: Learning objectives, materials, videos and evaluation buttons.
3. Material: Apperception and teaching materials in the form of text, images and learning videos.
4. Learning Video: Video related to poetry writing material, including examples of poetry reading.
5. Evaluation: Practice questions to measure students' understanding

C. Product Feasibility

Product feasibility testing involves expert validators, teachers and students. Data from the feasibility test shows that the teaching materials are considered very suitable by validators (95.6% and 94.7%), teachers (91.6%), and students (82.5%).

1. Validation

Validator One: Assessing content and language aspects with a result of 96.5%, indicating that the teaching material is very suitable for use. Validator Two: Assessing aspects of learning planning and media with a result of 93.7%, indicating that teaching materials are very suitable for use.

2. Due Diligence

Teacher: Assessing aspects of effectiveness, efficiency, systematics, language and appearance with a result of 91.6%. Students: Assess teaching materials and ability to understand the material with a result of 82.5%.

D. Product Revision

Revisions are made based on the validator's suggestions, including consistency in foreign language equivalents and the use of appropriate diction in teaching materials.

E. Final Product

This interactive poetry writing teaching material is in accordance with the learning outcomes of the independent learning curriculum, which aims to improve students' language, reasoning and writing skills. These teaching materials also refer to teacher books and student books published by the government, which are then developed according to the characteristics of students in each region.

Interesting and innovative learning is very important to increase students' interest and motivation to learn, as well as students' understanding. Interactive learning media such as videos and simulations can make learning more fun and effective, helping students practice language skills more easily. Therefore, it is hoped that this interactive teaching material can increase student activity and learning outcomes.

Table of Product Feasibility Test Results

No	Test Subjects	Assessment Aspects	Percentage of Trial Results	Average Percentage	Criteria
1	Expert Validator 1	Content Aspect	97,2%	96,5%	Very Worth It
		Language Aspects	95,8%		
2	Expert Validator 2	Learning Design	95,8%	93,7%	Very Worth It
		Media Aspect	93,7%		
3	Practitioner (teacher)	Effectiveness of Teaching Materials	93,75%	91,6%	Very Worth It
		Systematics of Teaching Materials	87,5%		
		Language Appearance Teaching materialsr	100% 88,8%		
4	Learners	Product Eligibility	81,3%	82,5%	Very Worth It
		Retention of material	83,7%		
Average trial results				91,3%	Very Worth It

Andrean Fahreza Nur Wicaksana et al, Development of Interactive Poetry Writing Teaching Materials with Smart Themed Differentiated Learning Design in Class X SMA Brawijaya Smart School

From the table above it can be concluded that the average score of the four research subjects is 91.3%. The validation results are included in the very feasible category and can be implemented as teaching material for writing interactive poetry with a SMART-themed differentiation learning design in class X SMA Brawijaya Smart School.

The main menu page displays the initial display of interactive poetry text teaching materials on the web consisting of titles and learning topics. Apart from that, there are also items such as home, goals, materials, videos, and evaluations. The following is the initial appearance of the interactive poetry text teaching material product on the web.

The introductory menu in the product contains buttons for learning objectives, materials, videos and evaluations that can be selected according to what is desired. This introductory menu is located at the bottom of the main menu page.

V. CONCLUSION

The results of developing interactive poetry writing teaching materials with Smart-themed Differentiated Learning Design in Class X SMA Brawijaya Smart School are:

1. Development of interactive poetry writing teaching materials with SMART-themed differentiation learning design in class c) product feasibility which includes validation, initial product revision, trials, and final product. Meanwhile, the development results have several main menus that can help students, such as homepage, introduction, learning objectives, materials, learning videos, and evaluation. This is in line with the stages of developing teaching materials using the Borg and Gall model.
2. Validation from experts and student trials can conclude that the development of interactive poetry writing teaching materials with a SMART-themed differentiation learning design in class X SMA BSS Malang is very suitable for use in the learning process.

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